

Age Grade and Management of Conflict in Elibrada, Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State

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Abstract

In African traditional societies, conflict is often seen as a threat to peace and social harmony. As a result, every effort is made to ensure peace and unity through traditional institutions such as age-grade associations. This study therefore assessed the Age Grade and Management of Conflict in Elibrada, Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State with particular focus on activities of four age grades in the Local Government Area. The study adopted a survey design and collected data from both primary and secondary sources. Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) were conducted with four age-grade groups, and In-depth Interviews (IDIs) were held with community leaders, chiefs, women leaders, and youth leaders. Secondary data were sourced from published books, journals, articles, and the internet. Findings revealed that the use of age grades in conflict management is highly effective in the the study area. The study also found that while age grades previously operated under unwritten constitutions, changes and continuity in their activities have led to positive transformation and development within the community. However, some age grades still function primitively without access to modern technologies. The research concludes that age grades in the study area have historically played significant roles in labor provision, community security, and the mobilization of male warriors for territorial defense, all of which remain vital to communal harmony and development. The study recommends, among others, that government should ensure that the operational mode of all age grades and clubs is constitutionally defined to prevent harmful traditional practices.

Keywords: *indigenous conflict management, age grades, peace-building, negotiation, mediation, traditional mechanisms.*

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Introduction

The social nature of the African man predisposes him to conflict. This inevitable aspect of human existence has led to the development of various techniques for managing tensions and fostering peaceful coexistence within communities. Every society, whether literate or illiterate, has its own methods and mechanisms for resolving disputes and maintaining harmony. In Africa, indigenous conflict management mechanisms rely on local socio-political actors and traditional, community-based systems of justice and control (Mengesha, et al (2015 and Oladipo 2022)). These structures help resolve disputes within and between communities without necessarily depending on state institutions or external structures (Zartman, 2000).

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Traditionally, conflict or disagreement is seen as a threat to peace and social harmony, as it disrupts accepted norms and values that guide interpersonal relationships. It is often believed that disharmony invites misfortune, famine, drought, or even death (Oladipo, 2022). As such, every effort is made to promote peace and unity through negotiation, mediation, arbitration, and adjudication often involving community members and traditional institutions. According to Otite and Ogionwu (2001), cross-cultural anthropological literature confirms that native norms and customs have long been used in dispute settlement and peace-building in African societies. Studies on dueling, negotiation, mediation, arbitration, adjudication, and reconciliation provide a clear picture of the variety of traditional mechanisms employed across communities.

Traditional societies in Nigeria, in particular, possess deep-rooted cultural systems for conflict management that predate colonialism. Many of these systems remain functional today, maintaining social balance even when modern institutions falter ((Oladipo, 2022). The Igbo societies, for instance, have accumulated a wealth of experience and established specific institutions to prevent and resolve conflicts through reconciliation and restorative justice. These mechanisms include family heads, councils of elders, chiefs, religious leaders, age grades, kinship structures, compensatory processes, and healing ceremonies (Azuonye, 2016; Elendu, 2022, and Uzoh & Iheanyi, 2024).

Despite the vital role of traditional conflict management systems, especially the age-grade institution, there is limited systematic research on their effectiveness. While scholars have examined other traditional mechanisms of conflict management in Nigeria — such as the *Agba* (elders) among the Yoruba in which few have focused on age grades specifically (Fayemi, 2009; Oladipo 2022). In Elibrada community, located in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State, one of the most prominent social mechanisms for managing conflict is the age-grade system (nde-uke). Its role as a veritable tool for maintaining continuity and stability in Elibrada has been well recognized by scholars (Agbegbedia, 2013). Age grades in Elibrada have played and continue to play significant roles in conflict management through crime prevention, law enforcement, and welfare development (Atuonwu, 2016). This central role in the community’s socio-political structure inspired this study, which explores their functions in managing conflict.

Much of the existing literature on conflict in the Niger Delta (e.g., Wosu & Erondu, 2016; Wordu, 2016; Peterside, 2016; Anikpo, 2015) has centered on land disputes, environmental crises, and the socio-economic consequences of oil exploration. Although these studies provide valuable insights into the nature of conflict in the region, none have assessed the role of traditional age-grade institutions in conflict management particularly in Elibrada, Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. This research therefore fills that gap by examining how age grades contribute to the management and resolution of conflict in the community. The study specifically sought to examine the role of age grades as indigenous institutions in conflict management, identify the methods used by age grades in managing conflicts, and explore the extent to which age-grade involvement contributes to conflict resolution in the study area.

Conceptual, Theoretical foundations and Review of Literature

The Concept of Conflict in Perspectives

Etymologically, the word conflict is derived from the Latin verb *confligere*, meaning “to clash” or “to engage in battle.” Scholars have offered various definitions of conflict, but a common theme among them is opposing interests between two or more parties. According to Joshua & Ajayi (2022), can be presented as a scenario in which what two parties in conflict are fighting for cannot be made available to the two of them at the same time, hence their goal(s) are incompatible and the resultant effect of this development is conflict. In every conflict there are parties to the conflict

and there is also a conflict realm- that is the social environment where the conflict takes place which is defined by context and process, It is to this extent that Audu (2010 & 2021) opined that conflict is inherent in all forms of social interaction.

Similarly, Burton (1990), cited in Agbegbedia (2013), defines conflict as a confrontation between individuals or groups arising from opposing ends or means. Conflict is a universal phenomenon, it is not limited to any particular region, religion, or race. Some of these marked conflicts include the Rwandan genocide, the Darfur crisis in Sudan, the wars in Liberia and Sierra Leone, and the Kosovo conflict in former Yugoslavia, the Traditional Approaches and Institutions to Conflict Resolution in Bakweriland, Fako Division, South West Region of Cameroon (Onyesom & Igbesi, 2015; Belie, 2024).

According to Coser (1957) as quoted by Szczecińska-Musielak (2016) defines conflict as a struggle over values and scarce resources, where each side seeks to neutralize or eliminate the other. He argues that conflict is a natural part of social interaction and may even contribute to change and adaptation, and that in summary, it is not conflict itself that is dangerous, but the rigidity of social structures that refuse to allow for conflict and its management. Similarly, Agbegbedia (2013) and (Belie, 2024) notes that conflict occurs in all societies, though its frequency varies. Some societies experience prolonged peace, while others face frequent outbursts of violence. Conflict, he adds, can be violent or non-violent, controllable or uncontrollable, and resolvable or persistent, depending on the circumstances.

In the Niger Delta, conflicts often arise from competition over resources, particularly oil. Wosu and Erundu (2016) identify the following as major drivers: struggles over oil wells, land disputes, chieftaincy tussles, and competition for employment and contracts. In essence, conflict is not inherently negative; its outcomes depend largely on how it is managed (Deutsch & Coleman, 2000). Also, Wosu and Erundu (2016) highlight struggles over oil wells, land disputes, and chieftaincy issues as major causes, while Ekpenyong (2011) points to land ownership, religious rivalry, and boundary disputes.

The Age-Grade Association

Age-grade system in Nigeria could be traced to the pre-colonial Nigeria that lacked informed governing body. Among the eastern section of Nigeria, it was a gerontocratic type of government where the oldest man in a given community ruled assisted by the council of elders. In the western section, while the Oba stayed at the top, and the town chiefs assisted him, the oldest male headed the clans and the sub-clans. In the northern section dominated by the Hausa/Fulani people, the Emirs and town heads ruled the people (Ijere, 2018). Suffice to say therefore, that the age-grade system is an age-long socio-cultural institution found across Nigeria.

In the South-East and South-South regions for instance, the age grade system is known by various local names such as *otnogbo*, *otuebiri*, or *uke* age grades consist of individuals born within a range of years who collectively pursue community development and social stability (Atuonwu, 2016). Members are bound by a constitution that guides their conduct, prohibits misconduct (e.g., theft, adultery, or violence), and enforces attendance at social events. Punishments include fines, suspension, or expulsion. Beyond maintaining discipline, age grades contribute to community development through road construction, market building, and security mobilization. They also serve as agents of peace and social control, complementing traditional rulers in governance (Mengesha, et al 2015 and Atuonwu, 2016).

According to Eleazu (2020), each generic age- grade takes a special name that helps define its position in the community, but relative to other age grades. Members of each age grade are meant to know one another fairly well, to choose leaders among their members, to meet regularly to

discuss issues of mutual or communal interest and should be willing to help one another and defend the community when the need arises (Nwachi, 2021 & Elendu, 2022).

African Traditional Methods of Conflict Resolution

African traditional conflict resolution methods include mediation, negotiation, arbitration, adjudication, and reconciliation.

- Mediation involves a neutral third party who helps disputants reach an agreement without coercion (Elendu, 2022).
- Negotiation emphasizes dialogue and compromise to maintain relationships (Olaoba, 2008).
- Arbitration allows respected arbiters to make binding decisions based on communal norms (Uzoh & Iheanyi (2024), and UN Peacebuilding Initiatives, 2022).
- Adjudication brings disputants before a council of elders or chiefs to decide matters, often focusing on reconciliation rather than punishment (Azonye, 2016, and Belie 2024).
- Reconciliation restores broken relationships and emphasizes the principle of “no victor, no vanquished” (Oladipo, 2022).

These traditional methods embody values of fairness, restoration, and social balance, distinguishing them from the retributive nature of Western legal systems.

Cultural Analysis Theory

This study is anchored on the belief that African values and norms are essential tools for effective conflict management. It adopts the Cultural Analysis Theory, which emphasizes understanding conflict within the cultural context of the people involved. According to Mezie-Okoye (2016), modern methods of conflict management have often failed, while traditional norms and values provide a more stable foundation for resolving disputes. Similarly, Eleazu, 2020 and Belie, 2024) assert that culture is a fundamental aspect of human consciousness that shapes people’s understanding of reality. They argue that analyzing events through their cultural significance enhances the effectiveness of conflict management.

In Nigeria, ethnic and inter-tribal conflicts have led to the loss of lives and property. However, such conflicts can only be effectively addressed when understood within the religio-cultural contexts of the people. Culture is dynamic — it evolves and adapts to new circumstances — and therefore, combining traditional and modern approaches often yields better results. Traditional conflict resolution mechanisms focus on community-level issues, such as disputes between families, villages, or clans. In Elibrada, these mechanisms, particularly the age-grade system, have proven to be deeply rooted in the community’s cultural and religious values. Hence, this study adopts the Cultural Analysis Theory as the most appropriate framework for understanding the role of age grades in conflict management.

The Role of Age Grade in Conflict Management

Conflict is an inevitable aspect of human interaction, and every society develops its own mechanisms for managing it. In Africa, traditional conflict management methods evolved within communities and reflect indigenous wisdom rather than imported systems (Nwachi, 2021 and Oladipo, 2022). In Elibrada, conflict resolution traditionally involves various institutions, including age-grade societies, family heads, women’s groups (*Umuada*), and the council of elders. These systems are still valued despite the introduction of modern courts, which are often seen as a last resort.

Peterside (2016), identifies poverty, corruption, marginalization, impunity, and the failure to prosecute violent offenders as major causes. Similarly, Salawu (2010) lists government neglect, oppression, domination, and nepotism as key triggers, while several other scholars listed weak state institutions, rising inequality, corruption, competition over scarce resources, poverty, unemployment, misrule, the erosion of community values, and environmental degradation contribute significantly to communal conflicts (UNDP, 2006; Håkan & Anders, 2025; Uzoh & Iheanyi, 2024).

Other drivers and sources of conflict in African societies are diverse and often interrelated. They may stem from family issues, chieftancy disputes, economic competition, environmental degradation, or inter-communal tensions (Mezie-Okoye, 2015). In the Niger Delta, oil exploration has caused environmental degradation, leading to agitation for cleaner environments and fair compensation. These Environmental and Oil-Related Conflicts agitations often escalate into violent conflicts between communities and oil companies (Mezie-Okoye, 2015). Inter-Communal Conflicts arises from boundary disputes and competition for natural resources have fueled numerous inter-communal conflicts in Rivers State — such as the Okrika-Ogoni and Eleme-Andoni crises. These conflicts often arise from encroachment on land or waterways and are exacerbated by ethnic and political differences.

The traditional African societies has a long and viral history of age-grade institution which has served as a vital mechanism for ensuring peace, reconciliation, and social order in the society. In Elibrada, age grades are responsible not only for resolving disputes but also for anticipating and preventing conflicts before they escalate. Their methods are rooted in the community's customs, traditions, and values, which emphasize restorative justice rather than punitive measures. The focus is on maintaining social balance, rebuilding relationships, and preserving harmony among community members.

Age grades operate through both internal and external mechanisms. First is through the Internal controls which rely on personal shame, moral values, and fear of supernatural repercussions for wrongdoing. The other one is the External controls which involve sanctions and actions taken by the group or higher traditional authorities to maintain discipline and order (Azuonye, 2016; Uzoh & Iheanyi. 2024). Similar practices exist among the Ohafia people of Igbo land, where male representatives (*ndi-ichi*) from various family lineages form a men's court or assembly known as *amali*. Headed by the *ezie-ogo* (male ruler), this body adjudicates conflicts and maintains community standards (Unya, 2017 and Eleazu, 2020).

In Elibrada, a comparable system operates: the *ezie-ogo* and his council serve as custodians of ancestral traditions and land. Young men, through the age-grade structure, function as the enforcement arm implementing the council's decisions, arresting offenders, and maintaining security. Disobedience to the age-grade's authority attracts fines or public reprimand (Mbah, 2013).

The age-grade's functions in conflict management include:

1. Crime Prevention and Law Enforcement– Ensuring compliance with community laws and customs.
2. Reconciliation of Disputes – Mediating interpersonal and family conflicts through dialogue and compensation.
3. Security Maintenance – Protecting the community from internal unrest and external aggression.
4. Community Development– Executing public works such as market construction, road repairs, and sanitation.

The age-grade also performs restorative roles, bringing disputing parties together to settle grievances, rebuild relationships, and prevent re-occurrence. Their authority is recognized by the community and backed by the council of elders. Among the Ohafia and Elibrada people for instance, age grades were once organized for warfare and territorial defense (Azuonye, 2016). Over time, they evolved into peacekeeping bodies responsible for maintaining internal order. Their dual role as both warriors and peacebuilders underscores their importance in sustaining community harmony (Atuonwu, 2016 and UN Peacebuilding Initiatives, 2022).

Thus, the age-grade institution continues to play a transformative role in traditional conflict management combining diplomacy, communal solidarity, and discipline to preserve peace and stability. Empirical studies (Olateju, 2013; Okodo, 2012; Mezie-Okoye, 2016; Obasi & Nnamani, 2015) affirm that indigenous mechanisms like the *Umuada* (women's groups) and age grades serve as vital instruments for peace-building. These systems are rooted in African values of fairness, communal responsibility, and respect for human dignity.

While Western models of conflict resolution often emphasize legal retribution and winner-loser outcomes, African traditional approaches focus on restoring relationships, rebuilding trust, and ensuring communal harmony. In the context of Elibrada, the age-grade system remains a cornerstone of local governance and conflict resolution. It embodies the community's moral code, reinforces unity, and provides a structure for maintaining peace, specific roles, strategies, and effectiveness of the age-grade institution in managing conflicts, thus highlighting its enduring relevance in traditional and modern African societies.

Research Methodology

This study adopted a survey research design, which involves collecting data from a sample of respondents to represent the views of a larger population, and allows for the systematic gathering of information about people's opinions, attitudes, and behaviors on specific issues. Data were collected through structured questionnaires, interviews, and focus group discussions (FGDs) involving members of different age-grade associations and community leaders such as traditional rulers, women leaders, and youth representatives who participate in community decision-making.

According to the Rivers State National Population Commission (NPC, 2006), Emohua Local Government Area has an estimated population of 201,901 people. While Elibrada represents a smaller subset of this figure, its age-grade system serves as a model for understanding indigenous conflict management mechanisms in the region. The purposive sampling technique was employed to identify key informants who are directly involved in age-grade activities and conflict management.

Primary data were collected through questionnaires, in-depth interviews (IDIs), and focus group discussions (FGDs) with community members, age-grade representatives, and leaders. The secondary data were obtained from textbooks, academic journals, research papers, theses, government publications, and online resources. These materials provided theoretical and empirical foundations that complemented the primary data and offered broader insight into traditional conflict resolution systems. The data collected were analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative approaches.

Results and Discussion

Presentation of Data

A total of 40 questionnaires were distributed, and all were duly completed and returned, representing a 100% response rate. The high rate of return was due to the researcher's personal

contact with respondents and the cooperation of community members. The data obtained were analyzed using simple percentages for quantitative responses and thematic analysis for qualitative data.

Social and Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

The demographic characteristics of respondents included gender, age, occupation, and educational background. The Gender distribution of the respondents revealed that, out of the 40 respondents, 62.5% were male and 37.5% were female. This reflects the gender balance typical of age-grade membership in the study area, where men are often more involved in community conflict management and enforcement activities, while women play supporting and advisory roles.

The ages of respondents ranged from 25 to 65 years, with the majority (60%) between 35 and 50 years. This age bracket represents the most active and influential members of age grades who participate directly in decision-making, mediation, and implementation of resolutions. The analysis of their educational levels showed that 25% had primary education, 37.5% had secondary education, 30% possessed tertiary qualifications, and the rest 7.5% had no formal education. This indicates that a large proportion of respondents are literate and capable of understanding both traditional and modern methods of conflict resolution.

The Role of Age Grades in Conflict Management

Findings revealed that age grades play significant and multifaceted roles in managing conflicts within the study area. Their activities cover areas such as:

1. **Mediation and Reconciliation:** Age grades serve as intermediaries in family, inter-personal, and inter-group disputes. They facilitate peace meetings, encourage dialogue, and ensure that grievances are resolved amicably.
2. **Maintenance of Law and Order:** The age grades act as the enforcement arm of the community. They ensure compliance with community laws, impose fines on defaulters, and maintain discipline among members.
3. **Community Development:** Beyond conflict resolution, age grades engage in community service projects such as market sanitation, road construction, and environmental cleanliness. These projects foster unity and reduce tension within the community.
4. **Security and Surveillance:** Age grades organize night watches and community patrols to prevent crime, theft, and boundary encroachment. Their involvement in local security builds trust and cooperation among residents.
5. **Restorative Justice:** Rather than punishing offenders harshly, age grades focus on restoring harmony between disputing parties. Offenders are required to apologize, pay restitution, or perform community service as a form of reconciliation. These roles align with the findings of Mezie-Okoye (2016), Unya (2017); Nwachi (2021; Oladipo, 2022), who assert that traditional African societies emphasize reconciliation and collective wellbeing in conflict resolution.

Methods Used by Age Grades in Conflict Management

Data from interviews and FGDs identified several indigenous methods employed by age grades in managing conflicts as earlier affirmed by other scholars (Anikpo, 2015; Atuonwu, 2017; Mezie-Okoye, 2016 and Nwachi, 2021) includes:

1. **Dialogue:** Encouraging open discussions between disputing parties.
2. **Mediation:** Using respected age-grade leaders as neutral facilitators.
3. **Investigation:** Gathering facts and evidence before taking decisions.

4. Sanctions: Enforcing fines, public apologies, or community service.
5. Reconciliation Rites: Performing cleansing or forgiveness rituals to restore peace.

These methods are deeply rooted in the customs of the people and have proven effective in maintaining community harmony. Respondents also noted that modern influences, such as mobile communication and legal awareness, have enhanced the efficiency of these traditional processes.

Furthermore, when asked whether age grades are effective in managing conflicts, 90% of the respondents agreed that they are highly effective, while 10% expressed mild reservations, citing occasional bias or lack of coordination among certain age groups. Overall, respondents agreed that age grades are a trusted and reliable institution for resolving conflicts at the community level. Their credibility stems from their historical authority, familiarity with community norms, and emphasis on peaceful coexistence, thus aligning with previous studies by Anikpo, (2015); Atuonwu (2017), and Nwachi (2021).

Challenges Facing Age Grades in Conflict Management

Despite their success, age grades in the study area faces several challenges that limit their effectiveness. These include:

1. Influence of Modernity: Western values and legal systems have reduced reliance on traditional institutions. Younger generations often prefer court settlements to communal mediation.
2. Financial Constraints: Limited funds hinder the execution of community projects and enforcement of sanctions.
3. Internal Rivalries: Competition among different age grades sometimes leads to mistrust and conflict.
4. Lack of Formal Recognition: Government policies rarely integrate traditional structures like age grades into formal peace-building frameworks, reducing their institutional power.
5. Erosion of Cultural Values: The decline in respect for elders and traditional authority among youths has weakened community cohesion.

These findings correspond with the views of Agbegbedia (2013) and Atuonwu (2017), who note that modernization and social change have challenged traditional governance systems across African societies.

The study's findings further reveal that age grades remain a vital component of traditional conflict management in the study area. Despite modernization and external influences, they continue to maintain peace and promote development through collective action and moral discipline. Their success lies in the communal nature of their operations which emphasizes dialogue, restitution, and reconciliation rather than punishment. This aligns with the Cultural Analysis Theory, which views conflict resolution as a culturally embedded process that reflects a community's worldview and values.

The study also confirms that the age-grade system serves as a bridge between traditional authority and the people, ensuring that decisions from the council of elders are implemented at the grassroots level. However, the gradual decline in youth participation, coupled with limited state recognition, poses a serious threat to the continuity of this indigenous system. Strengthening collaboration between traditional institutions and modern governance structures could therefore enhance the effectiveness of community-based conflict management in Elibrada and beyond.

The study revealed that:

1. Age grades are central to conflict management in Elibrada. They serve as mediators, enforcers of community laws, and agents of reconciliation.
2. Their conflict management methods include dialogue, mediation, investigation, sanctioning, and reconciliation rituals, which emphasize fairness, restoration, and communal harmony.
3. Age grades remain highly effective because they operate within the framework of indigenous norms, values, and beliefs that command respect and compliance.
4. Challenges faced by age grades include the influence of modernization, financial limitations, internal rivalries, lack of government recognition, and the erosion of cultural values among youths.

Despite these challenges, age grades continue to play a vital role in peace-building, community development, and the preservation of cultural identity in the study area. This goes to affirm the continued relevance of traditional institutions in conflict management and underscore the need to integrate indigenous systems into modern peace-building strategies.

Conclusion and Recommendations

It is therefore evident that age grades have long served as an effective and respected institution for conflict management in the area. Such that, their success lies in their ability to blend moral authority with communal responsibility, using culturally accepted norms and values to promote peace and reconciliation. This is unlike Western conflict resolution systems that focus on winners and losers, the age-grade system emphasizes restoration, forgiveness, and coexistence.

The study concludes that through dialogue and community participation, conflicts are managed in a way that preserves relationships and strengthens social bonds. It further highlights that modernization and the growing preference for formal legal institutions are gradually diminishing the influence of traditional systems. If not addressed, this shift could weaken community cohesion and erode cultural heritage. To this end, the integration of traditional mechanisms like the age-grade system into the formal governance structure would enhance sustainable peace and community development in the study area and in similar communities.

Based on the findings, the study recommends amongst others that:

1. Government should formally recognize and collaborate with age-grade associations in local peace-building and security efforts. Their inclusion in policy frameworks will enhance community participation in governance.
2. Capacity building training for the Age-grade members should in modern conflict management techniques to complement their traditional methods and improve efficiency should be intensified.
3. Financial support for the local government and community stakeholders should be adequately provided for the age grades to sustain their peace and development projects.
4. There should be continuous cultural education to revive respect for traditional institutions among the youth, ensuring the continuity of indigenous values.
5. The study calls for the scholars and community leaders to document the processes and outcomes of traditional conflict management practices to preserve them for future generations, so as to promote integration, inclusivity and long-term peace.

6. Finally, it calls for the promotion of gender inclusion in an age-grade system that is often male-dominated. It particularly sought greater involvement of women, especially through groups like *Umuada*, ultimately for a more balanced and holistic conflict management process.

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